

A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON THE MICROSTRUCTURE AND TENSILE PROPERTIES
OF HEAT TREATED PARTICULATE SILICON CARBIDE REINFORCED 6061
ALUMINUM COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Two particulate silicon carbide reinforced 6061 aluminum composites were heat treated to various conditions (solution-annealed, peak-aged and over-aged) and the effects of heat treatment on the aluminum matrix properties were monitored using diamond pyramid microhardness measurements. The results are compared to age hardening curves obtained for the monolithic wrought alloy. The matrix microstructure of the heat treated composites was characterized using optical microscopy, SEM and TEM. Tensile tests were conducted on heat treated specimens. The matrix microstructure was found to have a significant influence on the strength, ductility, work hardening characteristics and fracture behaviour of the SiC/aluminum composites. The yield strength of the composites heat treated to peak hardness of the aluminum matrix was more than twice the yield strength of the same materials in the solution-annealed condition. However the peak aging treatment resulted in a significant decrease in the tensile elongation. Fracture surfaces of the heat treated SiC/6061 aluminum tensile specimens were composed of cracked SiC particulates surrounded by dimpled aluminum. The fracture mechanisms operative in the aluminum matrix appeared to be strongly dependant upon the matrix aging condition. Solution-annealed composites showed shear fracture of the matrix whereas ductile fibrous failure of the aluminum matrix dominated the fracture surfaces of peak-aged specimens. The effects of SiC size and volume fraction on the tensile properties of the composites are also discussed.

KEYWORDS: Particulate Composites; Matrix, aluminum; Silicon carbide; Characterization; Failure mechanism.

1. INTRODUCTION

Aluminum alloys reinforced with particulate SiC can offer higher specific strength and stiffness compared with their unreinforced counterparts. Additional advantages in terms of more isotropic properties and greater ease of processing can also be expected over continuous fiber metal matrix composites. However, a

serious drawback of these materials lies in their low ductility, typically an order of magnitude less than that of the unreinforced alloys. While a significant amount of engineering data has been gathered on discontinuously reinforced aluminum composites, the understanding of the relationships between the composites' microstructure and mechanical properties is somewhat less developed.

In this study, the tensile properties of two SiC reinforced 6061 Al composites with different volume fractions and size distributions of reinforcement were evaluated under heat treatment conditions providing widely different work hardening characteristics of the aluminum matrix in order to determine the influence of these parameters on the ductility of this class of composite materials.

2. MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL

The composite materials were in the shape of plates (1.3 cm thick by 13 cm wide) fabricated by DWA Composite Specialties Inc. using a proprietary powder metallurgy and extrusion process. Chemical analysis was performed by dissolving the composite materials in HCl/H₂O₂ and filtering out the SiC particulate. The compositions (weight %) of the dissolved matrix alloys were as follows:

	Mg	Si	Cu	Fe	Cr	Ti	V
Plate 2810	0.68	0.2	0.263	0.103	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1
Plate 2921	0.76	0.3	0.399	0.123	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1
Unreinforced 6061 (1)	1.0	0.6	0.28	--	0.2	--	--

Particulate volume fractions and average sizes were determined by quantitative image analysis using a Quantimet 920 image analyser and are given below:

Material	Volume Fraction of SiC (%)	Mean Size of SiC (μm^2)
Plate 2810	29.4 \pm 1.41	4.72 \pm 7.98
Plate 2921	26.7 \pm 1.36	3.55 \pm 4.40

The particulates were uniformly distributed in both materials, with some areas of low local volume fraction of reinforcement (Fig. 1a and 1b). There was a tendency for the long axis of the particulates to be aligned parallel to the extrusion direction.

To establish the age hardening behaviour of the material, heat treatments were carried out on polished specimens. The specimens were solution-annealed at 530 \pm 5 $^\circ\text{C}$ for two hours in an argon atmosphere and quenched in water at 25 $^\circ\text{C}$. Aging was carried out in air at 205 \pm 2 $^\circ\text{C}$ for various periods of time and the specimens were air cooled to room temperature.

Microhardness measurements were carried out on polished specimens using a diamond pyramid indenter with a 50 gf load applied for 15 seconds. Indentations were made in the aluminum matrix between SiC particulates within 30 minutes upon completion of the heat treatment. Ten to twenty measurements were made on each specimen. The age hardening curves obtained in this manner were used to select heat treatment procedures corresponding to 0

temper (530°C/2 h + W. Q.) and T6 temper (530°C/2 h + W. Q. + 205°C/30 min + A. C.) conditions.

For tensile testing, small size round specimens with a gauge diameter of 6.35 mm, gauge length of 25.4 mm and button ends were diamond machined with their long axis perpendicular to the extrusion direction. The specimens were heat treated after machining and immediately tested, at room temperature, on an Instron Model 8562 frame at a strain rate of 1.68×10^{-4} s⁻¹. Fracture surfaces of selected tensile specimens were examined in the SEM and selected test pieces were sectioned parallel to the tensile axis and polished.

2. MICROSTRUCTURE

The distribution of intermetallic constituents in the as-fabricated SiC/6061 composites was examined using the back scattered electron mode (BSE) of the SEM, which provides atomic contrast images (Fig. 2a). Intermetallics appearing as black phases (1 to 5 μ m) were found, by EDAX analysis, to be composed of magnesium and silicon. These are probably Mg₂Si precipitated during processing of the plates. Large (1 to 5 μ m) phases having a white contrast in BSE images were composed of Al+Ti+V and Al+Fe+Si, as determined using EDAX analysis. The Al+Fe+Si intermetallics were also present as smaller (1-2 μ m) rounded phases. All three types of intermetallics were observed occasionally at the SiC particulate/Al matrix interfaces. There did not appear to be any difference in the intermetallic content of the two SiC/6061 composites. After solution annealing, the Mg and Si containing intermetallics were completely dissolved and only the Al+Fe+Si and Al+Ti+V inclusions remained undissolved, thereby reducing the volume fraction of large intermetallics in the material.

3. MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

3.1 Microhardness Figure 3 shows a plot of the microhardness of the aluminum matrix as a function of aging time at 205°C for the SiC/6061 composites. Peak hardness was reached after 15 minutes at 205°C for both the composite materials. For plate 2810, the matrix hardness was increased from about 77 kgmm⁻² (solution-annealed state) to 158 kgmm⁻² (peak-aged state) and for plate 2921, it was increased from about 83 kgmm⁻² (solution-annealed state) to 132 kgmm⁻² (peak-aged state). Increasing the volume fraction and the size of the SiC did not appear to modify the aging response of the matrix although the hardness values were systematically higher for plate 2810 (29.4% SiC) than for plate 2921 (26.7% SiC). This may reflect the influence of the SiC particulates being more closely spaced and therefore closer to the microhardness indentations in the higher volume fraction material. Monolithic 6061 aluminum fabricated by powder metallurgy (2) has previously been reported to achieve peak hardness after one hour aging at 205°C. The accelerated aging behaviour of particulate SiC reinforced aluminum has been reported by a number of other authors (2-4). When the composite is quenched from the solutionizing temperature, high residual stresses and high dislocation densities are generated in the matrix in the vicinity of the particulates, due to the thermal contraction mismatch between the aluminum matrix and the SiC reinforcement (5). The diffusion of age hardening elements is accelerated and heterogeneous nucleation of the precipitates on

the dislocations and at the SiC/matrix interfaces is enhanced, resulting in faster attainment of the peak hardness.

3.2 Tensile Properties Tensile tests were performed on specimens heat treated for 30 minutes at 205°C instead of the full peak hardness condition corresponding to 15 minutes aging. It was felt that this heat treatment would produce only slight overaging of the matrix, as shown by the age hardening curves on Fig. 3, and was easier to control, resulting in better reproducibility of the age hardening treatment.

Material	Temper	Y.S. (MPa)	T.S. (MPa)	Elongation (%)	Modulus (GPa)
2810	O	171±13	334±24	7.3±2.8	118±12
2921	O	189±4	365±3	11.1±1.5	107±8
6061 (1)	O	55	124	30	-
2810	T6	360±28	431±28	4.2±0.9	117±3
2921	T6	374±14	445±17	5.4±2.1	109±8
6061 (1)	T6	276	310	17	-

TABLE 1 TENSILE PROPERTIES OF HEAT TREATED SiC/6061 AND UNREINFORCED 6061

Table 1 lists the tensile properties measured for the solution-annealed and peak-aged materials. The T6 aging treatment (30 min/205°C) resulted in a substantial increase in yield strength of 190 MPa for plate 2810 and in an increase in yield strength of 185 MPa for plate 2921, as well as a more modest increase in tensile strength of 97 MPa for plate 2810 and 80 MPa for plate 2921. It is a well known characteristic of elevated temperature aging of aluminum alloys that the increase in yield strength is more pronounced than the increase in tensile strength. The increase in strength due to the T6 aging treatment was accompanied by a significant decrease in ductility: for both plate 2810 and 2921. The tensile elongation of the SiC/6061 composites after the T6 treatment was only half the value measured in the solution-annealed condition.

Table 1 also lists some tensile values for monolithic 6061 aluminum alloy (1). The peak-aged SiC/6061 materials show an 80-100 MPa increase in yield strength, an 120-135 MPa increase in tensile strength and a decrease in tensile elongation of about 12% compared with the unreinforced 6061 alloy. However, the ratio of the yield strength in the T6 condition to that in the solution-annealed condition is about 2 for the SiC/6061 materials whereas it is 5 for the unreinforced 6061 alloy. The strength increment due to the T6 aging treatment is therefore reduced in the MMC materials compared with the unreinforced 6061.

As expected, plate 2810, which had the highest volume fraction of reinforcement (29.4%) had higher elastic modulus than plate 2921 (26.7%). The elastic modulus of plate 2810 was 118±12 GPa and that of plate 2921 was 107±8 GPa, as measured from the linear portion of the stress-strain curves of solution-annealed specimens. Both materials showed a considerable increase in modulus compared with the unreinforced 6061 alloy. The elastic modulus of unreinforced 6061 is reported to be 68.3 GPa (1). The differences between the elastic moduli of T6 and solution-annealed SiC/6061 materials were within the specimen variabilities.

3.3 Fractography Detailed SEM examinations were conducted on fractured tensile specimens. Typical fracture surface and fracture profile appearances are shown in Fig. 4 to 7. For all material conditions, some specimens failed prematurely during testing, achieving lower than average strength values. In all of these cases, macroscopic features were observed on the fracture surfaces that could be correlated to the occurrence of defects in the microstructure such as cracks and non-consolidated areas, which are presumed to have resulted from the fabrication and processing of the material. Data for these specimens were included in the averaged values reported in Table 1.

The fracture surfaces of tensile specimens of both plates 2810 and 2921 in the T6 condition were composed of a bimodal dimple distribution (Fig.4a and 5a). Larger dimples were associated with the SiC particulates whereas the smaller dimples were associated with ductile fibrous failure of the aluminum matrix. Dimples associated with the SiC were only slightly larger in size than their parent SiC, indicating that separation occurred prior to any substantial void growth, as expected in low ductility materials. A significant number of the SiC particulates appeared to be covered with a thin, finely dimpled layer of aluminum. EDX analysis of such areas showed Si with small Al peaks, suggesting that failure had taken place in the matrix layer immediately adjacent to the SiC/Al interface. This type of particulate/matrix decohesion is expected when there is good bonding between the matrix and the reinforcement accompanied by a high density of void nucleation sites in the highly stressed matrix immediately adjacent to the SiC. Such a situation may arise when age hardening precipitates are heterogeneously nucleated at the SiC/matrix interface. Particulate/matrix decohesion was reported to be the dominant failure mechanism in over-aged SiC/7XXX P/M composites for which the occurrence of age hardening precipitates at the SiC/Al interfaces was demonstrated by TEM observations (6). The dimples in the matrix ligaments between reinforcement particulates were larger than the dimples on decohered SiC (Fig.4b and 5b), indicating that the spacing of the void nucleating defects was different in the matrix than at the SiC/Al interfaces.

A significant number of the SiC particulates visible on the fracture surfaces of the T6 tensile specimens had smooth surfaces. EDX analysis of such areas showed only Si peaks, proving that no matrix was adhering to these surfaces and that these were cracked SiC (see arrow on Fig.5b). Occasionally, secondary cracks were observed in SiC particulates on the fracture surfaces of both 2810 and 2921 specimens. Large cracked intermetallics were also occasionally observed.

The fracture surfaces of the solution-annealed specimens consisted of cracked and decohered SiC particulates surrounded by flat, relatively featureless matrix areas with some elongated dimples. The fractographic features of both solution-annealed materials were very similar. Many of the cracked SiC particulates lay at the bottom of elongated dimples (Fig.6). Fracture profiles of solution-annealed specimens showed that the fracture path proceeds mostly through the aluminum matrix and is not influenced by the presence of the SiC (Fig.7). The number of SiC particulates present on the fracture surfaces of the solution-annealed specimens also appears to be smaller than on the T6 specimens (compare Fig.6 to Fig.4a). In the case of the

solution-annealed specimens, the fracture plane was found to lie at an angle of about 50° to the tensile axis whereas fracture surfaces of T6 specimens were perpendicular to the tensile axis of the specimens. The fracture surfaces of solution-annealed specimens were obviously the result of shear failure of the matrix. In as-quenched magnesium-containing aluminum alloys, magnesium in solid solution is known to promote the formation of macroscopic shear bands during uniaxial tensile deformation.

4. DISCUSSION

The fracture initiation process in particulate hardened materials with high volume fractions of reinforcement has recently been reviewed (7). Two fracture models have been proposed for particulate reinforced composites. The first model is an extension of existing models for the ductile fracture of materials containing low volume fractions of reinforcement. In this model, voids are nucleated by particle/matrix decohesion and/or particle cracking followed by void growth and final coalescence (7,8). The second fracture model involves the initial failure of the matrix followed by fracture and/or decohesion of the particulates as the final step in the fracture process (9). In this case, void nucleation in the matrix is enhanced as a result of the high levels of plastic constraint imposed by the presence of the reinforcement.

Focusing on the void nucleation process in the first model, two important variables should first be considered: the matrix yield strength and the work hardening behaviour. Larger values of the matrix yield strength are expected to lead to increased void nucleation by allowing more particle/matrix interfaces to reach their decohesion stress or by increasing the amount of particle cracking. The work hardening behaviour will have a similar effect on nucleation because higher work hardening will result in greater stress at a given tensile strain. The effect will be greater in the vicinity of the particulates. Initial strain hardening rates of both 2810 and 2921 SiC/Al composites in the T6 condition were significantly higher than for the solution-annealed condition. At a true strain of 0.002, the strain hardening rates of the T6 composites were around 70 GPa whereas values around 35 GPa were obtained for the solution-annealed specimens. Furthermore, the yield strength of the T6 composites was twice as high as that of the solution-annealed composites (see Table 1). Void nucleation at the SiC particulates should therefore be favored in the T6 composites compared to the solution-annealed composites. A greater number of SiC particulates were experimentally observed on the fracture surfaces of T6 specimens than on those of solution-annealed specimens, although quantitative fractographic measurements should be performed to quantify the extent of this phenomenon.

The process of void nucleation has been reported to be more important than void growth in controlling the fracture of materials with reinforcement volume fractions greater than 0.1 (7,10). In void growth models, void coalescence is predicted to occur when the void length is equal to the interparticle spacing. In high volume fraction materials, the interparticle spacing is smaller. In the case of plate 2810, the interparticle spacing to particle size ratio is about one if a uniform distribution of the SiC is assumed. In areas of higher local volume fraction, an even smaller ratio will be found, resulting in severely limited

void growth before final fracture of such areas. The highly localized and catastrophic nature of this type of fracture process explains why very few voids were observed below the fracture surfaces of fracture profiles of sectioned tensile specimens which had been tested in the T6 condition.

The particulate size will play a secondary role in the fracture process by influencing the tendency for particulate cracking against particle/matrix decohesion. An increasing extent of particulate and void nucleation are expected with increasing particulate size due to the greater probability of finding a critical sized defect which would fail under lower applied stresses. This could explain why the tensile strength of plate 2810 (reinforced with larger SiC particulate) was not improved in comparison to that of plate 2921 (reinforced with smaller particulate) even though plate 2810 had the higher stiffness.

In the solution-annealed materials, the strong tendency for stress localization into macroscopic shear bands dominated the fracture behaviour, resulting in fracture surface characteristics apparently controlled by shear failure of the matrix with little contribution from the SiC. Voids were nucleated in the highly strained matrix adjacent to SiC particulates situated in the macroscopic shear band, resulting in shear failure of the matrix accompanied by decohesion of the particulate reinforcement. In the case of the larger SiC particulates, load transfer from the matrix to the particulates resulted in particulate fracture and in the growth of large elongated dimples around these fractured SiC. Similar observations have been reported for solution-annealed 30 vol% SiC/7091 composite made by powder metallurgy (11).

5. CONCLUSION

This study has shown that it is possible to obtain tensile elongations for SiC reinforced 6061 aluminum composites similar to those of the heat treated unreinforced alloys by selecting smaller reinforcements with a narrow size distribution and by using an aluminum matrix with low work hardening characteristics.

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7. REFERENCES

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Fig.2 Back scattered electron micrograph of as-fabricated plate 2810 showing :
 (1) Mg+Si intermetallics
 (2) Al+Ti+V and Al+Fe+Si intermetallics.

Fig.3 Plot of microhardness of the aluminum matrix versus aging time at 205°C.

Fig.4 Scanning electron fractographs of tensile specimen of plate 2810 tested in the T6 condition.

Fig.5 Scanning electron fractographs of tensile specimen of plate 2921 tested in the T6 condition.

Fig.6 Scanning electron fractographs of tensile specimen of plate 2810 tested in the solution annealed condition.

Fig.7 Fracture profile of a tensile specimen of plate 2921 tested in the solution annealed condition.

